

Trinervitermes sp. Nov

Snouted harvester termites

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

© D. Gergonne

Group: Insect

Size: 4 mm

Distribution:

Trinervitermes sp termites play an important ecological role in South African grassland and savanna ecosystems. As harvester termites, they contribute to nutrient cycling and soil structure by processing large amounts of dry grass, supporting ecosystem productivity and health.

Importance:

Trinervitermes sp termites are widely distributed across the summer-rainfall regions of southern Africa, particularly in savanna and grassland ecosystems. They are most abundant in warm, open environments and are largely absent from winter-rainfall regions and cooler, high-altitude areas.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 55.02 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 11.54 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 1.74 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.5% [Single: 96.2%, Duplicated: 3.3%]

BUSCO database: insecta

Assembly N50: 6 338.44 kilobases

Contig number: 3 563

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